

The Effects of Clear Quartz on Sleep and Emotions: An Exploratory Study

Original Research

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Abstract

This small study (n = 12) examined the potential effects of clear quartz on dream recall, restfulness upon waking, and emotional state. Unlike most previous research, this study applied a unique methodology focusing specifically on clear quartz and combining self-reported measures across consecutive weeks. In Week 1 (baseline), participants slept without the crystal under their pillow, and in Week 2 (experimental condition) they slept with the crystal under the pillow.

The study relates primarily to alternative medicine and psychology, with additional relevance to sleep research and placebo studies. The results suggest that clear quartz has no measurable effect on dream recall, restfulness, or emotional state.

These findings are important because they contribute to a field often characterized by uncertainty and claims of therapeutic benefit.

Key words: clear quartz, placebo, sleep quality, crystal healing

Introduction

Clear quartz (also called pure quartz, rock crystal, or crystal quartz) is a mineral composed of silicon and oxygen atoms arranged in a crystalline structure. It belongs to the quartz family, one of the most abundant mineral groups in the Earth's crust.

Crystals have long been used in spiritual and healing practices, yet only a limited number of scientific studies have investigated their effects. In particular, no psychological or metaphysical studies focusing specifically on clear quartz have been published. Consequently, the belief that clear quartz can improve sleep quality or emotional well-being remains unproven. Establishing clear scientific evidence, whether positive or negative, could provide valuable insights for medicine, psychology, and therapy. Investigating under-researched healing practices also deepens the understanding of human needs and well-being.

In addition to placebo responses, several other factors could contribute to the perceived effects of crystals. These include feelings of groundedness from contact with natural materials, the idea of energy exchange, evoking feelings of safety or familiarity, effects

from ritual use, aesthetic contributions to a relaxing environment, and symbolic reminders of specific intentions.

This article presents a small experimental study with clear quartz, reporting on its potential effects on sleep and emotional experience. The aim of the study was to determine whether clear quartz influences these outcomes and whether such influences differ across age, sex, and personal expectations.

Hypothesis: “If people sleep with a clear quartz under their pillow, they will remember more dreams upon waking and report fewer negative emotions in the morning compared to when they sleep without a clear quartz.”

Literature Review

The ‘healing effect’ of crystals is sometimes associated with the placebo effect [1] where an effect occurs “as a result of believing a treatment is real, combined with the body's natural ability to provide pain relief” [2]. “Even if they know it's not medicine, the action itself can stimulate the brain into thinking the body is being healed. And the more ritualized the treatment, the more serious and important it feels.” [3]

A study on gemstones and the placebo effect found that “Color and specific shape do not play any role in the selection of cure related usage.” [4]

In spiritual and esoteric contexts, crystals are often believed to exchange energy with humans [5]. However, such sources differ in detail: some claim crystals balance the frequency of the body’s electromagnetic currents [5], others describe crystals as redirecting energy flow to unblock stagnation and promote clarity, focus, and relaxation [6]. None of these claims are supported by peer-reviewed scientific studies.

Furthermore, it is believed that every crystal, as well as every human, has a different energetic frequency, which depends on size, composition and colour [7].

Clear quartz, which is used in this study, “has the ability to work with anything and everything” balancing and revitalising the physical, mental, emotional and spiritual planes [8].

However, these claims are based on beliefs that are not scientifically proven, and some sources even state that “any frequency a crystal might emit would be extremely small” compared to electrical current therapies. [6].

Although crystal healing claims remain unproven, physics research on crystals has shown “that a number of waves exists in the crystal all of which have the same frequency, polarization and direction” [9].

Method

This study employed an experimental survey design to examine the potential effects of clear quartz on sleep quality and emotional state. Twelve volunteers (male and female), aged between 11 and 73 years, participated in the study. Participants were recruited from the researcher's personal network and resided in different countries. Each volunteer received a heart-shaped clear quartz crystal by post (see Figure 1). The study survey, which included the study instructions, was provided online; some participants completed it digitally, while others printed it out and recorded their responses on paper.

Figure 1. Clear quartz crystal used in the experiment.

The crystal provided to each participant measured approximately 1.5 cm in length, 1.5 cm in width, and 0.5 cm in thickness, with a weight ranging from 2 to 3 g. At the beginning of the study, participants were asked to state their personal expectations regarding the experiment; in some instances, this question was answered retrospectively after the study had been completed.

During the first week, all participants completed the daily survey each morning for seven consecutive days under baseline conditions, without the use of the crystal. In the second week, participants were instructed to place the crystal under their pillow each night for seven consecutive nights while continuing to complete the same survey each morning. In several cases, a break was taken before beginning the second week of the study.

The survey administered each morning contained the following questions:

1. How many dreams do you remember from last night? (Please write an exact number, no guessing.)
2. How would you rate your overall emotional state upon waking up?

(Participants were asked to select one of the following statements)

- Very positive
- Positive
- Neutral

- Negative
 - Very negative
3. Which emotions did you mostly experience upon waking?
 4. Which of these statements best describes your physical state upon waking?

(Participants were asked to select one of the following statements)

- I feel very rested
- I feel a bit rested
- I feel tired
- I feel very tired

The independent variable was the presence or absence of the crystal. The dependent variables were dream recall, self-reported sleep quality, and self-reported emotional state upon waking. To reduce potential confounding influences, participants were instructed not to alter their diet, exercise, evening routines, medication use, sleep duration, or bedtime during the study. Data collection relied exclusively on participant self-reports from the daily surveys. Participation was voluntary, and participants were not required to justify or explain their individual responses.

Results

Across all measures, only very small differences were observed between baseline (Week 1, without the crystal) and experimental condition (Week 2, with the crystal). Mean values for remembered dreams, emotional state, and restfulness showed no consistent trend of improvement or decline when comparing the two weeks.

There were, however, notable differences between participants. The total number of remembered dreams varied substantially across individuals, but these differences were already present during the baseline week and did not appear to be influenced by the crystal.

The emotional state and feelings of restfulness showed minimal variation across weeks and participants. No systematic differences between male and female participants were observed. Three participants had missing data for parts of the study, which were excluded from the mean values.

The survey item “Which emotions did you mostly experience upon waking?” was frequently incomplete or vague, with responses such as “normal” or “better than yesterday”. Participants also varied in the way they responded, sometimes listing multiple emotions on one day and a single emotion on another. This inconsistency made it difficult to compare and analyse the data systematically; therefore, these results are not presented in the tables.

Regarding expectations, four participants had anticipated a positive change from using the crystal, while six expected no effect. These expectations did not correspond with the results, as no consistent improvement was observed.

The following tables provide the detailed results of all participants.

Table 1 presents the results from Week 1 (baseline, without the crystal under the pillow) and Week 2 (experimental condition, with the crystal under the pillow). The “remembered dreams, total” row indicates the total number of dreams recalled by each participant during the respective week. The “emotional state” and “restfulness” rows show the mean self-reported ratings of each participant across the week. Participant expectations regarding the crystal are reported in the bottom row. These expectations are presented as written by the participants, which explains their sometimes unspecific phrasing. The final column shows mean values across participants for each measure and a summary of participant expectations. All mean values were calculated from available data and rounded to two significant figures.

		P 1	P 2	P 3	P 4	P 5	P 6	P 7	P 8	P 9	P 10	P 11	P 12	Mean values
Week 1	remembered dreams, total	0	11	9	6	4	5	9	5	5	3	7	7	6
	emotional state	(2.8)	(2.4)	(3.0)	(2.7)	(3.0)	(3.0)	(2.6)	(1.4)	(2.0)	(2.9)	(2.3)	(3.3)	(2.6)
	restfulness	(1.9)	(2.8)	(2.6)	(2.4)	(2.6)	(2.3)	(1.6)	(1.1)	(1.6)	(2.1)	(1.6)	(3.3)	(2.2)
Week 2	remembered dreams, total	3	9	6	9	4	5	8	1	4	6	5	6	(5.5)
	emotional state	(2.0)	(2.0)	(2.0)	(2.6)	(2.9)	(2.9)	(2.0)	(2.2)	(2.1)	(2.6)	(2.0)	(3.0)	(2.4)
	restfulness	(1.7)	(2.0)	(1.9)	(2.3)	(2.0)	(2.1)	(1.3)	(2.0)	NA	(2.4)	(1.3)	(3.1)	(2.0)
Expectation regarding the crystal	expected no difference	expected improvement of sleep	expected difference: sleep difference	expected difference: fewer awakenings and feeling more rested in the morning	expected difference: improvement of sleep and enhanced dream recall	NA	expected no difference	NA	expected no difference	Four participants expected a positive change, six expected none.				

Table 1 NA = data not available.

Emotional state rated on a 5-point scale (1 = very positive, 2 = positive, 3= neutral, 4 = negative, 5 = very negative). Restfulness rated on a 4-point scale (1 = very rested, 2 = bit rested, 3= tired, 4 = very tired).

Table 2 presents the mean values of male and female participants separately, across Week 1 (baseline, without the crystal) and Week 2 (experimental condition, with the crystal). The measures are the same as in Table 1: total number of remembered dreams per week, mean emotional state, and mean restfulness. This table allows for comparison of gender differences in the results.

	Mean values (men)	Mean values (women)
remembered dreams, total	(6.4)	(5.6)
emotional state	(2.3)	(2.8)
restesness	(2.0)	(2.3)
remebered dreams, total	(6.0)	(5.1)
emotinal state	(2.3)	(2.4)
restesness	(2.0)	(2.0)

Table 2

Emotional state rated on a 5-point scale (1 = very positive, 2 = positive, 3= neutral, 4 = negative, 5 = very negative). Restfulness rated on a 4-point scale (1 = very rested, 2 = bit rested, 3= tired, 4 = very tired).

Table 3 presents the mean values of participants who expected an effect of the crystal compared with those who expected no effect. The measures are the same as in Tables 1 and 2: total number of remembered dreams per week, mean emotional state, and mean restfulness. This table allows for comparison of results in relation to participants' prior expectations.

		Mean values (expected a difference)	Mean values (expected no difference)
Week 1	remembered dreams, total	(7.5)	(5.2)
	emotional state	(2.8)	(2.7)
	restesness	(2.6)	(2.0)
Week 2	remebered dreams, total	(7.0)	(5.3)
	emotinal state	(2.4)	(2.3)
	restesness	(2.1)	(2.0)

Table 3

Emotional state rated on a 5-point scale (1 = very positive, 2 = positive, 3= neutral, 4 = negative, 5 = very negative). Restfulness rated on a 4-point scale (1 = very rested, 2 = bit rested, 3= tired, 4 = very tired).

Discussion/Analysis

The findings of this study suggest that placing a clear quartz crystal under the pillow does not have a measurable effect on dream recall, emotional state, or restfulness upon waking. Results varied considerably between individuals, but no consistent pattern was observed across participants.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The sample size was small (n = 12), which increases the likelihood that random variation obscured any potential effects. Data collection relied on self-reports, which are subjective and prone to bias. In addition, three participants provided incomplete data. Some survey questions were also difficult to analyse systematically: the open-ended item asking which emotions were experienced upon waking was often left unanswered or completed with vague responses. This inconsistency complicated comparison across participants. External factors such as diet, stress, daily routines, and sleep environment may also have influenced outcomes, despite the instructions to keep these factors constant. From a methodological standpoint, the small size of the crystal, variation in pillow size, and the fact that the crystals were not prepared prior to use in ways sometimes considered important in spiritual practice, may also have influenced results.

The hypothesis tested in this study was: *“If people sleep with a clear quartz under their pillow, they will remember more dreams upon waking and report fewer negative emotions in the morning compared to when they sleep without a clear quartz.”* This hypothesis was not supported by the results. No systematic differences were found between male and female participants, and expectations regarding the crystal did not align with the observed outcomes. These results contrast with a previous study on gemstones and the placebo effect, which found a positive correlation between healing outcomes and placebo responses [4]. In the present study, no correlation was observed between participants’ expectations and their results.

Future studies could be improved by increasing the sample size, providing participants with larger crystals, and ensuring that crystals are handled consistently before use. Stronger control of external variables such as sleep environment and lifestyle factors would also improve reliability. The survey could be revised to rely exclusively on structured, multiple-choice questions, which would ensure more consistent and comparable responses.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effects of clear quartz on sleep quality and emotional state. No effect was observed in the mean values, and no consistent pattern emerged in individual results.

These results are important because there is considerable uncertainty around “crystal healing,” and some people believe crystals can improve health and well-being. The present findings, however, suggest otherwise. At the same time, the study had several errors, which provide useful guidance for further research.

The methodology applied here allowed for comparison of individual results, helping to separate personal conditions from potential effects of the crystal. This is valuable because it shows that individual differences (such as a person who generally sleeps well or feels better regardless of the crystal) can influence results. Future research with larger, more controlled samples could apply a similar methodology to provide stronger and more reliable conclusions.

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